

Network of Inclusive COVEs on Circular Material Welding and Preventive Maintenance for Socially Safe, Resilient & Sustainable Automotive Manufacturing

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1. Weldnet Newsletter Template

NEWS HEADING

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CHECK OUR SOCIALS

Linkedin story

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2. Weldnet Flyer template

Network of Inclusive CoVEs on Circular Material Welding and Preventive Maintenance for Socially Safe, Resilient & Sustainable Automotive Manufacturing

As the circular economy becomes a central focus in European automotive manufacturing—especially in relation to iron and other metallic components—industries are increasingly adopting advanced circular material welding (CMW) practices integrated with preventive maintenance systems (PMS). These innovations aim to significantly reduce corrosion, infrastructure deterioration, and the failure of critical parts, thereby minimizing the risk of serious injury to both workers and end users. However, the European Union currently faces a major skills gap in this domain, with a shortage of over half a million qualified professionals.

Benefits of Advanced Welding Technologies

- **Addressing Skills Gaps:** It helps close the significant skills shortage in Circular Material Welding (CMW) and Preventive Maintenance Systems (PMS) within the European automotive industry, ensuring a qualified workforce.
- **Sustainable Production:** By focusing on sustainable practices, the project supports the adoption of circular and recycled materials in automotive manufacturing, contributing to greener, more efficient production methods.
- **Inclusive Training:** It provides upskilling opportunities for a diverse group of workers, including marginalized communities such as refugees, minorities, and individuals with disabilities, fostering greater inclusivity in the workforce.
- **Regional Economic Growth:** The CoVEs align with regional smart specialisation strategies, stimulating local economies and helping regions to meet their industrial and technological needs.

Approach

The WELDNET project's approach is to create a network of five Centres of Vocational Excellence (CoVEs) in key European regions to address the skills gap in Circular Material Welding (CMW) and Preventive Maintenance Systems (PMS) in the automotive sector. These CoVEs will provide both initial and continuing vocational training, aligned with regional industry needs and smart specialisation strategies. The project focuses on upskilling workers, including marginalized communities, to support sustainable, digital, and safe production practices. By connecting local industry needs with targeted training, WELDNET aims to foster regional skills ecosystems and build a qualified workforce for the evolving automotive sector.

JOIN WELDNET TODAY!

Be part of the movement driving innovation in circular material welding and sustainable manufacturing. Visit www.weldnet.eu to learn more and get involved today!

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Objectives of Weldnet

The objective of the WELDNET project is to address the skills gap in the European automotive manufacturing sector by establishing a network of five Centres of Vocational Excellence (CoVEs) in regions facing a shortage of qualified professionals in Circular Material Welding (CMW) and Preventive Maintenance Systems (PMS).

Empower Inclusive, Future-Ready Learning

WELDNET aims to design a holistic, learner-centred vocational education and training (VET) programme to upskill workers—especially people with disabilities, migrants, and individuals from minority groups—across the five partner regions. Focused on Circular Material Welding (CMW) and Preventive Maintenance Systems (PMS), the programme will address urgent labour market needs while delivering strong environmental and social impact. It will combine both initial training (IVET) and continuing education (CVET/reskilling), blending vocational skills with key lifelong learning competences.

Build Regional Skills Ecosystems Aligned with EU Priorities

WELDNET supports the transformation of each participating region into a robust skills ecosystem in CMW and PMS for the automotive sector. This will be achieved through strong, long-term public-private partnerships that reform regional VET governance. These ecosystems will help align VET centres with market, environmental, and societal demands—embedding them fully within regional innovation systems (the knowledge triangle). The ultimate goal: creating sustainable employment opportunities in line with the European Green Deal, Digital Strategy, ET Deep Tech Talent Initiative, and new EU Industrial and SME strategies.

Create a Collaborative EU Network of Vocational Excellence

WELDNET will establish a complementary, cross-border network of five Centres of Vocational Excellence (CoVEs) that work together to build inclusive, high-performing learning environments focused on CMW and PMS. These centres will collaborate through co-design, co-development, and mobility opportunities for both learners and trainers. United by shared goals of inclusion and industrial relevance, this network will contribute to major EU initiatives including the Automotive Skills Alliance, European Steel Skills Alliance, and Energy Intensive Industries Skills Alliance, delivering IVET and CVET programmes that respond directly to emerging industry and societal challenges.

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